

Design and Development of Advanced-Composite Shrouds

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ABSTRACT

Twenty-three new materials were evaluated as candidates for application as an improved debris-resistant layer on a shroud. Composite materials reinforced with fibers of carbon, Kevlar, or Nomex, and unreinforced "neat" resin systems, including advanced epoxies, polyurethanes, polysulfone, and blends of polyvinyl formal and epoxy, were studied. The latter resin performed best both as a composite and as a "neat" resin.

The data showed that debris erosion environments are critical to sizing those sections of the shroud subjected to high impact angles. Emphasis was, therefore, placed on improving the erosion resistance of the outer surfaces of the advanced composites. Unreinforced neat resin layers were found to provide considerably more resistance to erosion than did comparable composites. Also, limited pebble impact data indicated that a "neat" resin outer debris-resistant layer does not degrade the resistance of the overall system to pebble impact.

INTRODUCTION

Shrouds are used on launch vehicles to protect the payloads from launch environments that include aerodynamic heating, natural weather conditions, and impact by debris. The shroud must maintain its structural integrity in these environments as well as under normal air loads and the loads imposed by vehicle acceleration and shroud separation and jettison. Metals are the most commonly used materials for shrouds. Examples of their use include the 50-ft-long, 22-ft-diameter, biconic aluminum-skin-frame NASA Skylab shroud, shown in Figure 1, and the 50-ft-long, 10-ft-diameter, external-stringer-stiffened aluminum-skin NASA Universal Payload Fairing shroud, shown in Figure 2.

McDonnell Douglas Astronautics Company, Huntington Beach, California, has been evaluating composite materials for shroud application. The high strength and stiffness of today's advanced composites make them attractive alternatives to metals as materials for shrouds. Figure 3 shows a small shroud made of composite material. This shroud is a thin-walled, fiberglass, semimonocoque structure stiffened circumferentially by internal semicircular frames.

Early work showed that none of the state-of-the-art composite materials tested could be optimized to survive both the pebble and dust environments and

still exhibit competitive performance relative to metallic configurations. Materials that performed well under pebble impact were vulnerable to dust erosion (e.g., Kevlar epoxy) and materials that performed well in dust erosion (e.g., graphite epoxy) were vulnerable to pebble impact. Consequently, subsequent work emphasized the development of advanced materials and concepts that can survive both dust and pebble impact and, at the same time, maintain a weight advantage over metallic shrouds in other flight environments.

MATERIAL DESCRIPTION

The advanced shroud material design concept described in Reference 1 is shown in Figure 4. It consists of three discrete layers. The inner layer (the wall adjacent to the payload) serves as the primary structural load-carrying member. Both graphite- and Kevlar-reinforced composites are candidate materials for the structural layer. Although graphite epoxy provides greater stiffness than Kevlar epoxy, test data demonstrated that it is also more susceptible to fiber breakage, damage, and penetration from debris impact (Reference 1). (Current work was limited to the immediate fiber regime indicative of T300 and AS. Efforts with newer, high-strain graphite were not evaluated and may offer potential.)

The center layer of the trilayer design concept is a syntactic foam, which acts as a stress decoupler to limit debris impact damage to the inner structural layer. The syntactic foam evaluated in this and past efforts used a glass-microsphere-filled resin. To date, the properties of the stress decoupler layers have not been optimized. The outer layer in the trilayer design concept is designed to serve as an erosion-resistant barrier against dust and debris impact.

The material development of an outer layer more resistant to erosion and debris centered upon Kevlar reinforcement, because the data clearly suggested that potential performance in erosion and debris environments was greater with this Kevlar fiber reinforcement than with graphite fibers.

Table 1 is a matrix of the Kevlar and neat resin composite systems that were evaluated in both erosion and debris resistance tests. This material development effort emphasized improving the composite hardness by modifying the resin and/or reinforcement materials to enhance the adhesive and wetting characteristics of the reinforcement. A review of the movies taken in high-velocity dust erosion tests clearly showed that the erosion mechanism for the Kevlar-epoxy barrier layer was a repetitive peeling of individual fabric reinforcement plies from the surface. This suggested that the Kevlar reinforcement was the "weak link" in the system. A microphotograph of the Kevlar-epoxy surface, Figure 5, confirmed this observation. The photograph shows the Kevlar weave print of fabric left intact in the relatively hard epoxy layer.

DUST EROSION TESTS

Dust erosion testing provided supplemental data on several of the materials considered in Reference 1, and screened improved materials in terms of their relative performance under test environments. The testing was completed with a range of particle sizes 50 to 1000 microns. The test matrix included particle velocities of 2400 and 3900 ft/sec and specimen impingement angles up to 20 deg. To provide insight into the role of resin selection and its impact on erosion, several series of erosion tests on the neat resin system were evaluated (see Table 1).

Testing was completed in a continuous-flow arc-heated wind tunnel, where high-pressure air is heated in a 5-megawatt arc heater. Dust particles are injected upstream of the nozzle throat and are aerodynamically accelerated in a hypersonic nozzle with a low-expansion rate. A multiple-mount model positioning system with nine stings, which is enclosed in a test cabin, injects models into the tunnel flow. High-speed motion pictures (frame speeds

of 5000 ft/sec) in conjunction with control specimens instrumented with thermocouples were used to enhance data evaluations. The frontface surface temperatures of several of the test specimens were obtained with a pyrometer.

Material damage was assessed by pretest and posttest thickness and weight measurements, supplemented by visual and microscopic inspection. Based on the measured mass losses and/or total eroded thickness, mass loss ratios were computed for each material tested. (Here, "mass loss ratio" is defined as the eroded mass of the specimen divided by the mass of the impacting dust.)

The resulting mass loss ratios are plotted on Figure 6 for the "neat resin system" and on Figure 7 for advanced composites. The figures also show the average of all mass loss data for the Ke/.75 PVF + .25 Ep advanced composite from Reference 1 and this effort.

With reference to Figure 6, the data indicate the erosion of the neat resin 1:1 PVF/Ep blend was about 30% lower than for the neat resin 3:1 PVF/Ep system, or the corresponding Kevlar-reinforced composite. The 3:1 PVF/Ep neat resin and the Ke329/.75 PVF+.25 Ep performances were comparable.

The data on Figure 7 indicate that composite erosion performance was almost unaffected when Nomex fabrics were substituted for Kevlar. Unfortunately, these results do not obtain in pebble impact, where Kevlar-reinforced systems demonstrated vastly superior performance over Nomex.

The Ke329/.75 PVF + .25 Ep composites were tested at several impact angles after 0 sec, 10 sec, and 20 sec of exposure to clear air before being exposed to dust. As expected, the dust erosion performance decreased with increasing exposure to clear air (increasing specimen temperature).

PEBBLE IMPACT TESTS

In this test program, spherical granite pebbles, with 3/8- and 5/8-in diameters were projected at target test materials at velocities ranging up to 3000 ft/sec and over impact angles up to 20 deg. The launcher used was the same as that used in Reference 1, and was a powder gun. A schematic of the pebble impact test system is shown in Figure 8.

Results of the pebble impact test are presented in Table 2 for a neat PVF/Ep system, Nomex reinforcement, and trilayer designs with neat resin. This data base is supplemented by that contained in Reference 1 for a trilayer design of Kev/PVF + Ep, as well as graphite phenolic, graphite polyimide, and Kevlar epoxy. An effective graphical presentation, first used in Reference 1, noted a nondimensional parameter of t/d , shown in graphical form in Figure 9. (The nondimensional parameter t/d is defined as the thickness of the target divided by the diameter of the impactor.) A line is drawn between penetrated and non-penetrated data points and near the ballistic limit data points. The test material is penetrated for conditions falling below the line and is not penetrated for conditions above the line.

The single-point ballistic limit data (Table 2) for a Nomex-reinforced composite is shown in Figure 10. A dashed line parallel to the ballistic impact line for a Kev/75 PVF + .25 Ep is drawn through the single data point. The data for the Kevlar system is for a Style 329 fabric (as described in Table 1). The Nomex was similar to the Kevlar 329 fabric, with a fabric weight of 10.54 oz/yd². This compared with 8.8 oz/yd² for Kevlar Style 329.

ADVANCED COMPOSITE CONCEPTUAL DESIGNS

Concepts evaluated in this current effort included single, bilayer, and trilayer designs using various stiffening arrangements. Cross sections are shown in Figure 11. For convenience, the design configurations that were evaluated were referenced as Configurations B through G.

Configuration B, the baseline reference, was a metallic design that limits the skin temperature to 1100°F. Zee-section ring frames formed from sheet were used throughout.

The five advanced composite designs used a common hat stiffener arrangement and differ only in skin construction. Both the cap and legs adjacent to the skin cross section were thickened to provide the moment of inertia required for environmental loads.

Design Configuration C (stiffened single layer) uses a Ke/PVF skin to carry all loads. Design Configuration D consists of a stiffened bilayer, with a Ke/PVF outer layer to provide enhanced resistance to dust erosion. A Kevlar-epoxy inner layer, with its much higher modulus of elasticity, is provided in Configuration D to increase the buckling strength of the shell. Design Configuration E also uses a Kevlar-epoxy inner layer, but substitutes a neat PVF/epoxy resin for the Ke/PVF system in the outer layer. The neat resin system provides greater resistance to dust erosion, but possesses lower mechanical strength than Ke/PVF.

Design Configurations F and G are stiffened trilayer skins with a syntactic foam as the center layer to provide these designs with superior resistance to pebble impact. Configuration F is similar to Configuration G in that the outer layer is Ke/PVF, and the center layer is foam. However, the inner layer of Configuration F is graphite epoxy, rather than Ke/epoxy, in order to indicate whether the higher stiffness of graphite epoxy can offset its demonstrated lower performance in pebble impact relative to Kevlar epoxy.

These metallic and advanced composite designs are preliminary and are not to be considered optimized with regard to materials, geometry, or local environment. However, they are sufficient for the purposes of drawing conclusions concerning the relative ranking of concepts.

ANALYSIS METHOD

Conventional structural analysis methods were used for all designs to determine skin thickness requirements for thin-walled conical sections.

Mechanical properties for the materials used in this sizing analysis are shown in Table 3. These properties are room-temperature values; however, Figure 12 provides knockdown factors for the critical properties when the material is subjected to elevated temperatures.

The values shown in Table 3 are typical values for the types of layouts envisioned to meet detailed design requirements. The knockdown factors given in Figure 12 were used for all composites and represent the trend for many materials.

A 450°F maximum temperature limit was imposed on all the composite designs*. Most of the mechanical property data for the composite materials used in this study are for the room-temperature-to-350°F range, with some data available for temperatures in excess of 350°F. Elevated temperature tests on graphite-epoxy composites (T300/934) showed that the compressive modulus at 550°F was 30% of the room-temperature value. The somewhat lower 450°F temperature was selected as a maximum due to the limited amount of test data available on the composite materials under consideration.

*For the resin systems considered, it is felt that this design temperature limit could be increased to a somewhat higher value, due to short time exposure. But, at present no mechanical property data exists at the higher heating conditions/heating rates. Higher temperature resin systems (600°F) exist, but a data base in the erosion/debris environments under evaluation does not.

Flight loads experienced very late in time are approximately 10% of those experienced early in time. The compressive modulus at 450°F is approximately 50% of the room-temperature value. This allowed the buckling-critical advanced composite shroud to automatically withstand flight loads late in time when it was sized by either the flight loads encountered earlier in the flight or the 450°F maximum temperature limit very late in flight time. The analysis sequence used for the metallic design was the same as that used for the composite, except the maximum exterior surface temperature was restricted to 1100°F.

RESULTS

Two different combinations of loading conditions were considered in establishing the relative ranking of concepts. The first case subjected the shroud to flight loads and aeroheating only. The second case added encounters with pebble impact and dust erosion to flight aeroheating.

The thermal weight penalty took two forms. The first required increasing shell thickness to compensate for the decrease in material mechanical properties at flight elevated temperature, temperature effect on the modulus of elasticity being the most significant. The second thermal weight penalty was due to the maximum temperature limitations of 450°F for the composite and 1100°F for the metal. It was often necessary to increase the skin thickness, especially on the forward and mid sections, to provide sufficient mass so that the shell temperature would not exceed its maximum allowable value.

For the condition of aero flight loads, (i.e., flight loads plus aeroheating), all composite shroud configurations are significantly lighter than the baseline referenced metal design, in some cases by as much as 50%. The result is reflected in all sections of the shroud, fore cone to aft cone. Preliminary analysis indicates that the trend for a composite shroud to weigh substantially less than a metal one would not be altered if higher design allowables were used for metal (e.g., 25%).

The pebble impact and dust erosion environments had a minimal effect on the metal design but were the major driver for all composite designs, especially in the forward and mid sections of the shroud. The percentage of weight attributed to structural and thermal requirements in the fore and mid sections was minimal, in comparison to the percentage of weight attributed to dust erosion.

When a single design configuration was used throughout the shroud, the metallic design proved to be lighter. This result is attributed solely to the dominance of dust erosion resistance in the sizing of all composite materials tested.

All composite designs were heavier than the baseline reference metal configuration. Weight reductions were not achieved by using a trilayer design approach (Configurations F and G), as a result of the dominance of dust erosion resistance in sizing. Preliminary analysis indicates that as the erosion resistance of the outer layers increased or if the trajectory/environment were reduced in severity, the trilayer design approach would yield lower weights than the bilayer configuration, as well as compete favorably with metallic designs.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Testing, analysis, and trade studies have verified a significant advance in the application of alternative materials (composites) to advanced launch vehicles, particularly with regard to their resistance to dust erosion and pebble impact. For example, a neat PVF/epoxy toughened resin system developed during this effort provides pebble impact resistance comparable to that of

similar Kevlar-reinforced composites, but it results in a 30% increase in erosion at high angles of attack. The design trade studies indicate that an all-composite shroud weighs more than a metallic shroud. The expectations for weight reduction for a composite shroud are high, based upon the improvements made to date in erosion resistance. The relative weights calculated for the composite shrouds are sensitive to the magnitude of the environment and the models used, particularly at high angles of attack. The major portion of the fore and mid section composite shroud weight results from the need to be protected against erosion. Moderate improvements in erosion resistance at high angles of attack would substantially change the ranking of composite shrouds versus metal shrouds.

The most attractive composite design is a bilayered composite consisting of a neat PVF/epoxy outer layer and a Kevlar/epoxy inner layer. The dominance of the erosion environment in sizing would not permit the more structurally optimum composite configuration, i.e., a trilayered design, to show a larger weight savings. Analysis indicates that with only moderate improvements in dust erosion resistance of composites, at high-angle-of-attack conditions, the advanced composites in a trilayered configuration have potential for weight reductions. This would result in competitive weight tradeoffs relative to metal. Specific conclusions are as follows:

- Alternative Nomex fabric reinforcement offered no advantage over the Kevlar-reinforced composites for erosion resistance and exhibited lower resistance to pebble impact.

- Improvement has been made in the erosion resistance of composites, relative to the data developed under previous programs (Reference 1), but significant weight reductions still did not accrue for composite designs relative to metal. Modest improvements in dust erosion resistance or a reduction in the severity of the environments will result in favorable weight reductions for advanced composites.

Additional development is required to improve the dust erosion resistance of the outer layer of a composite shroud in order to meet the high-impact-angle dust requirements of shroud sections. This would permit the more structurally optimum design configuration, the trilayered cross section, to demonstrate its potential for weight savings relative to metals.

REFERENCES

1. D. G. Giedt and L. J. Cohen, "Advanced Missile Material Response", 11th National SAMPE Technical Conference, Boston, Mass., 13-15 November 1979 (Printed in Conference Proceedings).

Table 1
Summary of Materials Screened in Current Program

Type	Description
<u>Composites</u>	
Ke329/.75 PVF+25Ep	Kevlar 329 with 3:1 mix PVF + epoxy, 45% resin content by weight.
Ke329/.5PVF+.5Ep	Kevlar 329 with 1:1 mix PVF + epoxy, 45% resin content by weight.
Kevlar 329/Hysol ADX 3130	Kevlar 329 impregnated with an experimental epoxy resin system with reported improved "wetting", 50% resin content by weight.
Kevlar 329/Hysol EA9323	Kevlar 329 impregnated with DuPont Adeprene L-100 polyurethane, 50% resin content by weight.
Kevlar 329/Adeprene L-100	Kevlar 329 impregnated with DuPont Adeprene L-100 polyurethane, 50% resin content by weight.
Kevlar 329/Hysol EA9332	Kevlar 329 impregnated with Hysol EA9332 Polyurethane, 50% resin content by weight.
<u>"Neat" Resins</u>	
1:1 PVF + epoxy	50% by weight each mix of PVF and epoxy
3:1 PVF + epoxy	Same as above except 3 parts PVF to 1 part by weight epoxy.
P-1700 Polysulfone	Compression-molded polysulfone.
Hysol EA9323	Cast epoxy.
Hysol ADX 3130	Cast epoxy.
Hysol EA 3909A	Cast flexible epoxy.

Table 2
Pebble Impact Test Results

Pebble		Impact		Target				T (°F)	Damage Code
Size (in)	Wt (g)	Deg	Vel (ft/s)	Material	Size (in)	Mass (g)			
						Pre	Post		
.610	4.754	20	1800	Trilayer 1*	6x5x.375	200.5	198.0	R.T.	5
.618	5.074	20	1700	Trilayer 1*	6x5x.375	197.4	195.9	R.T.	5
.615	4.919	20	1685	Trilayer 1*	6x5x.375	197.5	196.6	R.T.	4
.612	4.971	20	1530	Trilayer 2**	6x5x.355	209.5	209.2	R.T.	4
.615	4.906	20	1540	Trilayer 2**	6x5x.355	207.8	206.6	R.T.	5
.618	4.890	20	1231	Trilayer 2**	6x4x.355	183.22	183.2	R.T.	3
.522	3.159	20	600	N/PVF+EP***	4x5x.125	53.41	53.41	R.T.	2
.525	3.195	20	911	N/PVF+EP***	4x5x.125	55.14	55.03	R.T.	4
.509	2.883	20	1035	N/PVF+EP***	4x5x.125	53.23	53.13	R.T.	5

*Debris layer is .11 in. thick 3:1 PVF/epoxy neat resin.

**Debris layer is .08 in. thick 3:1 PVF/epoxy neat resin.

***Nomex/.75 PVF+.25Ep

NOTE: PEBBLE IMPACT DAMAGE CODE

1. No penetration, crater in front face.
2. No penetration, slight delamination.
3. Near penetration, delamination and backface fiber breakage.
4. Near penetration, moderate delamination, ballistic limit.
5. Penetration and severe delamination and fiber breakage.

Table 3
Typical Room-Temperature Material Properties

Material	E _c MSI	G MSI	μ	Density (lb/in ³)
Metal	16.0	6.2	0.31	0.160
K _e (329) PVF/0.75 PVF + 0.25 EP	2.0	0.14	0.12	0.0473
Ke/Epoxy	5.4	0.36	0.14	0.0488
Gr/Epoxy	8.5	1.40	0.13	0.0560
Neat PVF/EP	0.5			0.0440
Syntactic Foam	*	*	*	0.0094

Figure 1. Aluminum-Skin-and-Frame Shroud-Skylab

Figure 2. Aluminum Skin, External Stringer Universal Payload Fairing

Figure 3. Fiberglass-Epoxy Shroud

Figure 5. Microphotograph of a Dust-Erosion-Tested Kevlar-Epoxy Composite

Figure 4. Layered Material Concept

Figure 6. Summary of Mass Loss Ratios "G" for Various Neat Resins

Figure 7. Summary of Mass Loss Ratios "G" for Various Composites

Figure 8. Schematic of Pebble Impact Test System

Figure 9. Ballistic Limit for Shroud Materials at 20-Degree Impact Angle

Figure 10. T/D Versus V for Various Advanced Kevlar and Nomex Composites

Figure 11. Shroud Conceptual Design Concepts

Figure 12. Effect of Temperature on Material Properties - Knowdown Factor